

Modelling of energy use and greenhouse gas emissions from a quick service restaurant

Elias EID^{*(a,b)}, Alan FOSTER^(a), Graciela ALVAREZ^(b), Robin CAMPBELL^(a), Judith EVANS^(a)

(a) London South Bank University, Churchill Building, Bristol, BS40 5DU, UK, eide@lsbu.ac.uk*

(b) Université Paris-Saclay, INRAE, FRISE, 92761, Antony, France

ABSTRACT

Efficient refrigeration and cooking equipment and other innovating technologies in the food service sector need to be considered to reduce energy use and greenhouse gas emissions. In quick service restaurants (QSRs), there is a strong interaction between the structure, internal machinery, customers, and the store HVAC system. The impact of these interactions was modelled using EnergyPlus in a UK-based QSR, validating results against other research studies. It explored the effects of applying carbon saving technologies and predicted climate change impacts and grid conversion factors from 2020 to 2050. Findings revealed that among the individual technologies applied, enhanced efficiency of 20% in refrigeration and kitchen equipment gave the most favourable outcome, contributing to a 15.6% reduction in carbon emissions. Results also showed that combining technologies could achieve 39.7% savings in carbon emissions while predicted changes in electrical carbon factors could potentially yield 98.5% reduction in carbon emissions between 2020 and 2050.

Keywords: Refrigeration, Food service, Mathematical model, EnergyPlus, Energy use, Greenhouse gas emissions

1. INTRODUCTION

Studies indicate that 26-35% of global greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions can be attributed to food and agriculture, with approximately 18-29% of these emissions arising from the food supply chain (Poore and Nemecek, 2018; Crippa et al, 2021). According to Foster et al. (2023), refrigeration-related greenhouse gas emissions in the food service sector accounted for 1.93 MtCO₂e in 2019. Hence, it remains essential to find solutions for reducing these emissions within the food service sector.

The food service industry has various subsectors, including restaurants, pubs, clubs, cafes, hotels, leisure establishments, staff canteens, and those in the health care and education sectors. Within this industry, food and beverages are primarily kept refrigerated using small-scale systems, with integrated refrigeration systems such as beverage coolers and food display cases, as well as small split systems like cellar cooling in pubs and compact walk-in cold stores (Foster et al., 2023). According to UNOX (2023), around 73% of gas consumption is attributed to cooking, while over half of the electricity used in restaurants is dedicated to cooking and refrigeration.

Based on CIBSE (2012), and Mudie et al. (2013), commercial kitchens are among the most resource-intensive users of gas, water, and electricity in the UK. They also stated that they can significantly contribute to reduce carbon emissions, since they surpass energy benchmarks (in kWh/m²) by more than ten times compared to most other commercial premises.

In this context, a research and innovation project within the European Union (EU) is exploring ways to significantly reduce GHG emissions within the food industry by 2050. The ENOUGH (European food chain supply to reduce GHG emissions by 2050) project has been established to align with the EU's Farm-to-Fork

strategy and offer a comprehensive approach to transform the European food sector into an environmentally friendly, resilient, healthy, and equitable system.

The aim of this work was to assess the impact of various opportunities to reduce carbon emissions from a UK QSR and to determine how close to carbon neutrality it could achieve by 2050. The paper presents results from an EnergyPlus building model (US Department of Energy, 2022) that examines the impact of external and internal environmental conditions on energy consumption and carbon emissions from a QSR when new carbon saving technologies were applied. The impact of changes to climatic temperature and changes to the electrical grid conversion factor from 2020 to 2050 were also presented.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A QSR located in the UK was modelled using EnergyPlus software. It served as a baseline model and was validated against various research studies. Section 2.1.3 demonstrates the model inputs used for the baseline, outlining parameters sourced from references, real QSR data, assumptions, expert advice, or default values provided by EnergyPlus.

2.1. Modelling of the QSR

2.1.1. Methodology

The total energy consumption for the modelled scenarios was calculated using EnergyPlus V22.2.0. SketchUp Pro 2023 (Trimble Inc.) was employed for drawing and creating the model geometry, while OpenStudio V1.5.0 (by NREL, ANL, LBNL, ORNL, and PNNL) was used to incorporate and adjust various properties such as weather files, construction, materials, occupancy, internal loads, schedules, water systems, HVAC, and refrigeration systems. The environmental impact was characterised by the total equivalent warming impact (TEWI).

2.1.2. Geometry

The geometry was derived from architectural plans containing all the required dimensions. The QSR had a floor area of 431 m² and was divided into 10 zones: chiller, corridor, dining room, drive-thru, freezer, kitchen, office, staff room, store, and WC, with areas of 16 m², 25 m², 179 m², 10 m², 18 m², 88 m², 9 m², 25 m², 21 m², 40 m², respectively (Figure 1). The height of all zones was 4.5 m.

Figure 1. Geometry of the QSR with its space types

2.1.3. Model inputs

This section presents the model inputs. Further and more detailed information is provided in Table 1.

London weather files for both 2020 and 2050 were used to evaluate the effects of climate change. <https://weathershift.com/> was used to shift the historical EnergyPlus weather files to 2020 (considering current climate change) and forward to 2050 (considering predicted future climate change). The 2050 weather files employed a representative concentration pathway (RCP) 4.5 and 8.5. RCP 4.5, according to the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), highlights moderate emissions peaking around 2040 and then decreasing. RCP 8.5 portrays a significant increase in emissions.

OpenStudio encompassed various parameters such as the outlet operational hours, occupancy, lighting, equipment usage, and specific operation times for various components. All electrical devices were added in OpenStudio as electrical input loads.

To define the envelope of the fast-food restaurant, a recent standard construction set from the American Society of Heating, Refrigeration and Air Conditioning Engineers (ASHRAE) within the library was employed (90.1-2019 – ASHRAE 169-2013), using materials from OpenStudio's built-in libraries. These default materials included concrete, gypsum, typical Insulated wood, etc.

The hot water system included a pump, a service water loop comprising an electrical resistive water heater on the supply side, and area connections for water use on the demand side. The daily water consumption was taken from the QSR.

By default, HVAC systems and components such as flow rates, heating and cooling capacities are "auto sized" by EnergyPlus using sizing algorithms. These are derived from heating and cooling loads at design conditions from the weather files. The HVAC aims to control each thermal zone via a thermostat set point. Heating was electrical from heat pumps and two packaged rooftop heat pump units (PRHP) were considered for the kitchen and the dining room. The supply side of these HVAC systems had a cooling coil, a heat pump, a supply fan, and an outside air system. On the demand side, the kitchen and the dining rooms were connected using zone air terminal units. Each of the remaining areas was regulated by a packaged terminal heat pump unit (PTHP), which is a ductless, through-the-wall heating and cooling system.

The COP of the heat pump was calculated based on the outside temperature (T) using a cubic equation from default values in EnergyPlus:

$$COP_{T, heating} = \frac{COP_{rated, heating}}{1.192 - 3.004e-2 T_d + 1.037e-3 T_d^2 - 2.333e-5 T_d^3} \quad \text{Eq. (1)}$$

where $COP_{T, heating}$ is the COP at different temperatures, $COP_{rated, heating}$ is the COP at rated conditions (outdoor air dry-bulb temperature of 8.33°C) and T_d is the outdoor air-dry bulb temperature in °C.

The COP of the cooling coil was calculated based on the outside dry-bulb and wet-bulb temperatures using a biquadratic equation from default values in EnergyPlus:

$$COP_{T, cooling} = \frac{COP_{rated, cooling}}{0.3424 + 3.488e-2 T_w - 6.237e-4 T_w^2 + 4.977e-3 T_d + 4.379e-4 T_d^2 - 7.280e-4 T_w T_d} \quad \text{Eq. (2)}$$

where $COP_{T, cooling}$ is the COP at different temperatures, $COP_{rated, cooling}$ is the COP at rated conditions (air entering the cooling coil at 19.4°C wet-bulb temperature and air entering the outdoor condenser coil at 35°C dry-bulb temperature), T_w is the wet-bulb temperature in °C, and T_d is the dry-bulb temperature in °C.

The QSR had two cold stores: a chiller, and a freezer operating on R448A direct expansion (DX) systems. The refrigeration system was divided into two racks. One rack served the low temperature (LT) needs for the freezer, while the other served the medium temperature (MT) requirements for the chiller. Each system was equipped with an air-cooled condenser with a variable speed fan and one compressor. The sizing of the condensers was determined by considering a temperature difference of 10K between the condensing

temperature and the ambient temperature. The maximum rated fan power was assumed to be 3% of the heat rejection based on Foster et al. (2018).

Figure 2 shows the refrigeration DX systems of the chiller and the freezer.

Figure 2. Chiller and freezer refrigeration DX systems

Details of the model inputs are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Model inputs

Opening hours	From 6 am – 10 pm (Monday-Sunday)		QSR data
Internal heat loads		Lighting load consumption (kWh/year)	Electric load consumption (kWh/year)
	Corridor	436	194
	Dining room	7,189	30,066
	Drive Thru	233	350
	Kitchen	5,494	134,753 343,783
	Office	206	308
	Staffroom	561	844
	Store	558	372
	WC	930	133
Heating thermostat	21°C (kitchen) 20°C (all the other areas)		QSR data
Cooling thermostat	23°C (all the areas)		QSR data
HVAC system	Cooling DX Rated COP	3	EnergyPlus default
	Heating DX Rated COP	2.75	Expert advice
	Fan total efficiency	0.7	EnergyPlus default
	Controlled thermal zones	All areas	QSR data
	Heating design supply T	40°C	EnergyPlus default
	Cooling design supply T	15°C	EnergyPlus default
Hot water system	Water consumption: 2,200 L/day Specific heat capacity of water = 4.185 J.K ⁻¹ .kg ⁻¹ Inlet T: 11.15°C Target T: 60°C		QSR data At average T _{35.6°C} Mean ambient T EnergyPlus default
Refrigeration system (R448A)	Compressors	Copeland-DISCUS-LOW_2DB3-060E-TFD Copeland-DISCUS-MEDIUM_3DF3-120E-TFD	EnergyPlus default

	Evaporating T	Chilled/Frozen: -8°C/-33°C ¹	Footnote 1
	Minimum condensing T	21°C ²	Footnote 2
	Refrigerant charge (kg)	3.2 ³	Footnote 3
	Refrigerant leakage for cold stores (/year)	10% ⁴	Footnote 4
Cold stores (Chiller and freezer)	Total area	Chiller/Freezer: 16 m ² /18 m ²	QSR data
	Operating T	Chiller/Freezer: 3°C/-18°C	QSR data
	Height of doors	2 m	EnergyPlus default
	Cooling coil capacity	4690 W	EnergyPlus default
	Fan	735 W	EnergyPlus default
	Light	120 W	EnergyPlus default
	Defrost	2500 W	EnergyPlus default
	Insulated floor heat transfer U: 0.207 W/m ² .K		EnergyPlus default
	Insulated surface U facing zone: 0.235 W/m ² .K		EnergyPlus default
Stocking door U facing zone: 0.3785 W/m ² .K		EnergyPlus default	

2.2. Total equivalent warming impact (TEWI)

The TEWI characterises CO_{2e} emissions and is a useful tool to study the impact of systems on global warming. The TEWI combines the direct and indirect emissions of CO_{2e}. TEWI is based on the following relation:

$$TEWI = (GWP \times m \times L) + (E \times \beta) \quad \text{Eq. (3)}$$

Where *TEWI* is the mass of CO_{2e} produced during a year (kg); (*GWP* × *m* × *L*) are direct emissions of CO_{2e} due to refrigerant leakage; (*E* × *β*) are indirect emissions of CO_{2e} associated with electrical energy consumption; *GWP* is the Global Warming Potential of the refrigerant; *m* is the refrigerant charge of the QSR (kg); *L* is the leakage rate per year; *E* is the electrical energy consumption per year of the QSR (kWh/year); *β* is the CO_{2e} equivalent emissions per kWh of electrical energy produced (kg CO_{2e}/kWh). A GWP of 1273 (100-year horizon) for R448A was taken from the IPCC AR5 report (2013). Electrical carbon emission factors for the UK between 2020 and 2050 were taken from the UK BEIS (2023).

Table 2 summarises the predicted electrical carbon factors for the UK between 2020 and 2050.

Table 2. Predicted electrical carbon factors for the UK

	2020	2025	2030	2035	2040	2045	2050
β (kg CO _{2e} /kWh)	0.197	0.131	0.049	0.020	0.016	0.008	0.003

¹ CO₂ Product Guide 2021 for Refrigeration. Emerson. Applications co₂-product-guide-2021-for-refrigeration-applications-en-gb-4217772.pdf (emerson.com)

² Petersen, Michael; Pottker, Gustavo; Sethi, Ankit; and Yana Motta, Samuel F., "Refrigerants With Low Environmental Impact For Commercial Refrigeration Systems" (2018). International Refrigeration and Air Conditioning Conference.

³ The refrigerant charge was calculated using the F-Gas refrigerant charge calculator excel file - Guidance on impact of the fluorinated gas regulation for users of stationary refrigeration, air conditioning and heat pump. Taken from: General Guidance F Gas and Ozone Regulations. Information Sheet GEN 5: Refrigerant Quantity, April 2012.

⁴ https://uk-air.defra.gov.uk/assets/documents/reports/cat09/2105061125_ukghgi-90-19_Main_Issue_1.pdf

2.3. Model calibration

The overall annual energy consumption from the model was validated against the real QSR data. The modelled total annual energy consumption was found to be 44.6% lower, compared to the validation data. The QSR didn't provide any information regarding electrical equipment and therefore, EnergyPlus default values were used. However, the QSR manager mentioned that kitchen equipment accounted for the highest portion of energy usage overall, exceeding that of HVAC systems. Therefore, an assumption was made that the difference might be the quantity of electrical load in the kitchen. To address this, an adjustment was made by increasing the electrical load in the kitchen (an increase of 2.55-fold) to fit the real annual QSR total energy consumption (Table 1). The calibration was only carried out on total energy consumption, as the QSR had no sub-metering.

Table 3 presents the monthly energy consumption from the real QSR and the monthly energy consumption predicted by the model after calibration.

Table 3. Monthly data of the validation and simulated UK QSR after calibration

Month	Validation data (kWh)	Simulated data (kWh)	% difference
Jan	45,338	47,362	4.5%
Feb	41,340	43,003	4.0%
Mar	42,098	46,646	10.8%
Apr	47,900	45,307	-5.4%
May	48,345	47,064	-2.6%
Jun	45,860	45,794	-0.1%
Jul	51,763	48,122	-7.0%
Aug	50,597	47,761	-5.6%
Sep	46,010	45,440	-1.2%
Oct	45,865	46,628	1.7%
Nov	44,210	45,193	2.2%
Dec	46,051	47,294	2.7%
Total	555,377	555,614	0.04%

2.4. Modelling technologies

The impact of various carbon saving technologies incorporated in the QSR were examined individually and together to assess their effects. The technologies examined were:

- Technology 1: Increase dead band temperature of the HVAC by 2K, by increasing cooling and decreasing heating set points by 1°C.
- Technology 2: Low GWP refrigerant (GWP=150). It was assumed that the QSR's energy usage would be the same as that of the baseline running on R448A.
- Technology 3: 20% more efficient refrigeration and kitchen equipment.
- Technology 4: Maintenance/operational practices. The sole difference from technology 3 was the % efficiency in refrigeration and kitchen equipment, which was assumed to be 10%.
- Technology 5: Economizer in the HVAC. Economizers were integrated into the HVAC of both the kitchen and dining areas. These used outside air to provide free cooling when the external air conditions were favourable, instead of relying on the mechanical cooling of the air conditioning.

- Technology 6: Renewable Energy Sources. Solar photovoltaic (PV) panels were installed on the fast-food establishment's roof, covering an area equivalent to the roof's total area. The electricity generated was calculated using the RETScreen software tool. RETScreen uses published local data for daily solar radiation on a horizontal surface in kWh/m².day for each month. Using the location (London) and orientation of the panels together with their efficiency (assuming a 15% efficiency), the output for each month is calculated. The total output for the year is the sum of these values.
- Technology 7: All the technologies above were combined in a single model to understand their potential impact on energy use and carbon emissions.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Validation of the baseline QSR model with research studies

Mudie et al. (2013) presented comparisons of benchmarks among various licensed restaurants and pubs. Annual electricity use was plotted against total floor area and kitchen area. Their research revealed that establishments with a comparable total floor area had annual energy consumption ranging from 180,000 to 560,000 kWh. Similarly, establishments with a kitchen area similar to the QSR, had annual energy consumption ranging from 120,000 to 560,000 kWh. These results show the validation of our model of 555,614 kWh/year that falls at the top end of these reported ranges.

BEIS (2016) stated in their Building Energy Efficiency Survey (BEES) that 5 million square meters (m²) of restaurants and takeaways consume a total of 5,890 GWh of total energy per year. Based on this information, we can calculate their Energy Use Intensity (EUI) in terms of site energy. The mean energy EUI comes out to be 1,178 kWh/m², compared to 1,289 kWh/m² in our case study (9% difference).

It is worth noting that the energy consumption of the QSR was on the high side in both studies due to the QSR being in the top 10% sales of the chain, thus having a very high turnover.

The majority of the simulated QSR's energy consumption (68%) was consumed by interior equipment. The internal heat loads, particularly in the kitchen, meant that cooling rather than heating in the restaurant was required throughout the year. These findings underscore the importance of implementing technologies to evaluate the interaction between the structure, internal machinery, and the store HVAC system and assess their influence on energy consumption and carbon emissions. The CO_{2e} emissions were predicted to be 109.9 t CO_{2e}/year. Figure 3 shows the divisions between the energy using components for the modelled QSR.

	Energy consumption (kWh/year)
Heating	17,769
Cooling	56,606
Interior lighting	15,611
Interior equipment	376,056
Fans	19,828
Pumps	28
Water systems	45,506
Refrigeration	24,214
Total annual energy	555,614
TEWI	109.9 t CO _{2e} /year

Figure 3. Energy consumption and TEWI of the QSR

3.2. Technologies

Table 4 show the impact of energy saving technologies applied individually to this “baseline” model and then combined to assess their impacts on energy use and carbon emissions.

Technology 1 led to changes in heating, cooling, and fan consumption. Despite this, the overall energy consumption showed a 1.7% reduction primarily because interior equipment had the greatest impact on energy usage. Consequently, the QSR’s TEWI was reduced by 1.8% compared to the baseline.

Technology 2 resulted in a 0.3% reduction in CO_{2e} emissions. This was due to the relatively small refrigerant charge (3.2 kg).

Technology 3 led to changes in heating, cooling, and fan consumption, and an 18.3% reduction in overall interior equipment energy use and a 20.0% in refrigeration use. This led to a 14.8% decrease in overall energy consumption. As a result, carbon emissions were reduced by 15.6%. This outcome was due to the reduction in interior equipment energy consumption, which holds the largest share of energy consumption in the QSR.

Technology 4 led to a 7.4% decrease in total energy use. As a result, carbon emissions were reduced by 7.8%.

Technology 5 resulted in 74.3% reduction in cooling consumption and a 7.5% decrease in total energy consumption. The cooling usage in the QSR was primarily influenced by the high heat output from the electrical loads in the kitchen, which demanded extensive cooling throughout the year. However, with the addition of an economizer, the necessity for mechanical cooling decreased especially during colder months. Consequently, the TEWI was reduced by 7.5%.

Technology 6 estimated 61,633 kWh/year energy savings from RETScreen. The annual energy consumption was then reduced by 11.1%. It led to an 11.0% reduction in carbon emissions. This shows the viability of using solar PV even in regions far from the equator.

Technology 7 gave a 39.5% reduction in total energy consumption compared to the baseline scenario. Consequently, carbon emissions were reduced by 39.7%.

Table 4 shows the results when carbon saving technologies were applied to the baseline QSR.

Table 4. Table showing a summary of all the simulations

Technology	Baseline	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
	Energy consumption (MWh/year)							
Heating	17.8	14.7	17.8	18.5	18.1	18.1	17.8	16.0
Cooling	56.7	52.4	56.7	44.8	50.7	14.6	56.7	8.8
Interior lighting	15.6	15.6	15.6	15.6	15.6	15.6	15.6	15.6
Interior equipment	376.0	376.0	376.0	307.3	341.7	376.0	376.0	279.8
Fans	19.8	17.5	19.8	17.5	18.7	19.8	19.8	14.6
Water systems	45.5	45.5	45.5	45.5	45.5	45.5	45.5	45.5
Refrigeration	24.2	24.2	24.2	19.4	21.8	24.2	24.2	17.4
RES	-	-	-	-	-	-	-61.6	-61.6
Total	555.6	546.0	555.6	468.6	512.0	513.9	494.0	336.1
	TEWI (t CO_{2e}/year)							
	109.9	108.0	109.5	92.7	101.3	101.7	97.7	66.3

3.3. Future decarbonisation of the QSR

The impact of climate change and the grid conversion factors were assessed for the baseline and combined models. An assumption was made that the design of the current QSR would not change and only electrical grid carbon intensity and climate changes that are already predicted would be applied.

3.3.1. Impact of climate change

The results for the baseline QSR are presented in Table 5. The other sub-metering parameters were not displayed in the table as they remained unchanged. While variations were observed in heating and cooling consumptions, the rise in total annual energy consumption was only 0.02% for the most dramatic climate (RCP 8.5) and 0.05% for the least dramatic (RCP 4.5). This was attributed to a balance between increased cooling demand and reduced heating requirements in the QSR resulting from the effects of climate change.

Table 5. Differences in energy for the 2050 weather files compared to the baseline

	Energy consumption (MWh/year)				
	2020	2050 (RCP 4.5)	2050 (RCP 8.5)		
			% change	% change	
Heating	17.8	16.5	-7.30%	15.1	-15.17%
Cooling	56.7	58.0	2.29%	59.1	4.23%
Refrigeration	24.2	24.4	0.83%	24.5	1.24%
Total	555.6	555.9	0.05%	555.7	0.02%

3.3.2. Impact of changes to electrical grid conversion factor

Changes to the electrical grid carbon factors for the UK were applied from 2020 to 2050 (Table 2). The predicted CO_{2e} emissions for the baseline QSR decrease significantly from 109.9 t CO_{2e} in 2020 to 2.1 t CO_{2e} in 2050. Similarly, for the combined model, the emissions drop from 66.3 t CO_{2e} in 2020 to 1.1 t CO_{2e} in 2050 (a reduction of 98.5%) (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Predicted CO_{2e} emissions in the UK QSR from 2020 to 2050

The results highlight the potential for achieving near-zero carbon emissions in both scenarios, either by doing nothing or employing combined technologies. It is clear that without implementing any technologies, the QSR could potentially reach near-zero carbon emissions by 2050 purely through the projected changes in

electrical carbon factors. However, the rate at which carbon emissions decline is important. Not applying or applying late these technologies results in higher cumulative carbon emissions. This underscores the significance of initiating technology implementations as soon as possible to reduce cumulative emissions.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The main objective of this work was to accurately model the total energy consumption of a UK QSR using EnergyPlus and study the impact of various technologies to reduce energy consumption and GHG emissions. The focus was also to determine how close to carbon neutrality the QSR could become by 2050.

Among the findings, kitchen equipment emerged as the largest contributor to energy usage in the establishment. Adjusting the store's dead band temperature to reduce heating and cooling needs, resulted in only a 1.8% reduction in carbon emissions. Similarly, employing a low GWP refrigerant had a mere 0.3% impact on emissions due to the relatively small refrigerant charge in the restaurant's cold stores. The use of more efficient equipment due to maintenance and operational practices, led to a 7.8% reduction, whereas higher efficiency equipment resulted in a 15.6% decrease in carbon emissions. These two outcomes were mainly due to the increased efficiency of equipment, which accounts for the restaurant's major energy consumption. The addition of solar panels on the establishment's roof led to an 11.0% decrease in carbon emissions. Incorporating economizers into the HVAC systems significantly reduced cooling consumption by 74.3%, especially during colder months when free cooling from the outside was used instead of the HVAC mechanical cooling, resulting in a 7.5% reduction in CO₂e emissions. Combining all these technologies demonstrated a notable 39.7% decrease in carbon emissions.

Despite achieving a 39.7% reduction in carbon emissions in the combined model compared to the baseline in 2020 and a projected 98.5% total carbon emission reduction in the UK from 2020 to 2050 based solely on predicted changes in electrical carbon factors, this alone isn't sufficient to reach zero emissions. Failing to implement any technologies would result in higher cumulative carbon emissions. Hence, initiating technology implementations is essential to reduce emissions and ensure energy savings. Ongoing research is examining additional technologies and their impact when implemented across food catering establishments in Europe.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The work within this paper received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101036588.

NOMENCLATURE

ANL	Argonne National Laboratory
ASHRAE	American Society of Heating, Refrigeration and Airconditioning Engineers
BEES	Building Energy Efficiency Survey
BEIS	Business, Energy and Industrial Strategy
COP	Coefficient of performance
CO ₂	Carbon dioxide
DX	Direct expansion
EU	European Union
EUI	Energy use intensity
GHG	Greenhouse gas
GWP	Global warming potential
HVAC	Heating, ventilation and air conditioning
IPCC	Intergovernmental panel on climate change
LBNL	Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory

LT	Low temperature
MT	Medium temperature
NG	Natural gas
NREL	National Renewable Energy Laboratory
ORNL	Oak Ridge National Laboratory
PV	Photovoltaic
PNNL	Pacific Northwest National Laboratory
PRHP	Packaged rooftop heat pump
PTHP	Packaged terminal heat pump
QSR	Quick service restaurant
RCP	Representative concentration pathway
T	Temperature
TEWI	Total equivalent warming impact

REFERENCES

- CIBSE, 2012. Guide F Energy Efficiency in Buildings. The Chartered Institution of Building Services Engineers (CIBSE) 222 Balham High Road, London SW12 9BS, 2012.
- Crippa, M., Solazzo, E., Guizzardi, D. et al. 2021. Food systems are responsible for a third of global anthropogenic GHG emissions. *Nature Food*.
- Foster, A., Brown, T., Evans, J., 2023. Carbon emissions from refrigeration used in the UK food industry, *International Journal of Refrigeration*, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijrefrig.2023.01.022>
- Foster, A., Hammond, E., Brown, T., Maidment, G., and Evans, J., 2018. IIR - Technological options for retail refrigeration. Paris International Institute of Refrigeration/ London South Bank University; Road Map Technologies report, 26 January 2018.
- IPCC, 2013. *Climate Change: The Physical Science Basis. Contribution of Working Group I to the Fifth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change* [Stocker, T.F., D. Qin, G.-K. Plattner, M. Tignor, S.K. Allen, J. Boschung, A. Nauels, Y. Xia, V. Bex and P.M. Midgley (eds.)]. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, United Kingdom and New York, NY, USA, 1535 pp. <https://www.ipcc.ch/report/ar5/wg1/>
- Mudie S., Essah EA., Grandison A., Felgate, R., 2013. Benchmarking Energy Use in Licensed Restaurants and Pubs. Chartered Institute of Building Service Engineering (CIBSE) Technical Symposium 2013. Liverpool John Moores University, UK, 2013.
- Poore, J., Nemecek, T., 2018. Reducing food's environmental impacts through producers and consumers. *Science*, 360(6392), 987-992.
- BEIS, 2016. Building Energy Efficiency Survey BEES: Hospitality sector, 2014-15.
- BEIS, 2023. Valuation of energy use and greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. Supplementary guidance to the HM Treasury Green Book on Appraisal and Evaluation in Central Government.
- UNOX, 2023. Energy savings and lower Co2 emissions in catering: the 5 steps that can reduce the carbon footprint of your business. Accessed from: https://www.unox.com/en_gb/blog/reduce-carbon-footprint-of-business-in-5-steps/
- U.S. Department of Energy, (2022). EnergyPlus Engineering Documentation Reference. Build: ed759b17ee.